

YOUNG PEOPLE OF NEW UZBEKISTAN ARE THE FOUNDATION OF OUR FUTURE AND PROSPECT

Tursoatova Shahrizoda Bakhtiyor kizi

Denov district of Surkhandarya region

11th grade student of school 101

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Abstract: In this article, while analyzing the reforms implemented in the field of youth policy, we see the interdependence of the state and youth, ensuring the employment of youth in every direction. All the reforms of our country were described in order to create the necessary conditions for boys and girls to grow up in all aspects and get education.

Key words: Uzbekistan, State, youth, politics, reform, law and order, decision, maturity, education, president, renaissance, science, supreme assembly, dedication.

The future of the young generation has always been at the center of Uzbekistan's state policy. Even today, large-scale reforms in all spheres are being carried out rapidly in order to eliminate the problems that have arisen in our country, to create conditions that positively affect the development and education of young people.

Uzbekistan is truly a country of youth. Young girls growing up in this country have many dreams and goals. The initiative and support of the head of state will help them realize these goals. President Shavkat Mirziyov: "As we have set ourselves the great goal of establishing the foundation of the Third Renaissance in our country, for this we must create the environment and conditions that will educate new Khorezmians, Berunis, Ibn Sinas, Ulugbeks, Navoi and Babur. First of all, the development of education and training, the establishment of a healthy lifestyle, and the promotion of science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea", his words opened the way for young people to achieve great goals.

In order to effectively spend the free time of young people, to familiarize them with the rich heritage of our ancestors, and to instill feelings of love and pride for the motherland, under the leadership of teachers of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Qudratullo Abduraimov and Dilnoza Khudoyberganova, the youth of Beshkapa neighborhood visited the Museum of Honor located in Victory Park. Young people have always been recognized as an active layer of society. Their role was incomparable in the period of the Eastern Renaissance, in the activities of the moderns, and in the renewal of society. In

this respect, this regularly forming layer requires constant guidance and support.

Analyzing the reforms implemented in the field of youth policy, we can see the inextricable connection between the state and the youth. Employment of young people continues in every direction. Necessary conditions are being created for boys and girls to develop in all aspects and get education. This is important for them to become a generation that will contribute to the development of the country in the future.

Young people are the future of any society. Literally, they are the greatest wealth, priceless treasure of Uzbekistan. After all, the young people of Uzbekistan are the foundation of our future and prospects. Today, in our country, all efforts and opportunities are being used for their perfect mastery of modern science and high technologies, in particular, there is a great meaning behind the establishment of presidential and creative schools. Now we can be rightly proud of the achievements of young people studying in educational buildings equipped with modern requirements and with all conditions.

The fact that Firdavs Abduqayumov, a student of the President's School in Tashkent, scored a high score in the IELTS program and became the recipient of a \$96,000 grant to study at the John Carroll University of the United States, clearly proves how correct the path we have chosen in the field of education under the leadership of the head of our country in a short time is.

It is not for nothing that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in his address to the Oliy Majlis put forward the idea that "New Uzbekistan starts from the threshold of the school, from the educational system." Already, as our head of state noted, "If we can combine the knowledge and experience of the older generation, the qualities of foresight with the enthusiasm, courage and selflessness of our youth, we will definitely reach the desired goals."

From this point of view, today the deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis are actively working to ensure the implementation of the priority tasks stated in the Petition. In particular, after this historic speech, a number of events dedicated to the content and importance of the Petition were held in the lower house of the parliament.

Yesterday, at the inter-factional dialogue on the topic "Education and upbringing - the foundation of the maturity of the young generation and the guarantee of the development of our country", the tasks specified in the Address were discussed in detail. In a sincere and high-spirited dialogue, along with the tasks included in the Address, A number of suggestions for the development of

the education system were made in the draft of the State Program for 2030. It's not for nothing, of course. It is clear that achieving the goals defined in the Petition requires unanimity and activity from all of us.

Why do you say that, during our meetings with local residents, we have witnessed many times that the buildings of most schools were built in the middle of the last century, the desks are old, and there are not enough classrooms. Therefore, since science, education and upbringing are the forces that make the country powerful, improving the conditions of schools, which are the place of knowledge and spirituality, is a task that cannot be postponed.

In the petition, it was mentioned that the reforms to fundamentally improve school education and increase its quality, to create decent conditions for teachers, will be continued rapidly. Of course, the allocation of 2 trillion soums from the budget for the purpose of building 30 new schools, repairing 320 schools and improving their material and technical base this year has clearly touched the hearts of thousands of young people. In order to continue the work started in this direction, the announcement of 2021 as the "Year of Youth Support and Public Health Promotion" in our country has given new strength and inspiration to the efforts of young people to show their potential.

In our opinion, supporting the construction of sports, music and art schools for children due to the rapid development of public-private partnerships and private services in the field, especially in the field of in-depth teaching of English, computer science, mathematics and other high-demand subjects, will use the huge potential of the private sector. It will definitely pay off in a short period of time.

In short, if we look at the history of the developed countries of the world, we will see that the reforms aimed at changing the life of the society started with the education system. The foundation of education and training is the school. In this regard, the quality of education in schools should be high both in the capital and in remote villages.

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